

COVID-19 and Education in Afghanistan: Responses and Obstacles

Kardan Journal of Social
Sciences and Humanities

4 (1) 44–56

©2021 Kardan University

Kardan Publications

Kabul, Afghanistan

DOI:10.31841/KJSSH.2021.4

<https://kardan.edu.af/Research/CurrentIssue.aspx?i=KJSSH>

Mohammad Ajmal Khuram

Received: 10 May 2021

Revised: 24 May 2021

Accepted: 12 June 2021

Abstract

The onset of the Covid-19 pandemic has affected the education system at the primary and tertiary levels in Afghanistan. The containment measures that included maintaining physical distance led to the closure of schools. While many institutions have tried to manage the issue through online and remote learning, the absence of adequate infrastructure has derailed the recovery process. This qualitative study explored the impacts of Covid-19 on the education system in Afghanistan and how online has helped address the disruption in normal learning. Semi-structured interviews were used to collect data from 11 study participants representing different education sectors in the country. The study results indicate that the closure of schools in Afghanistan due to the Covid-19 pandemic had resulted in a significant loss of learning time and disruption of the academic calendar. The effort to use online learning was also ineffective as there is a lack of necessary infrastructures such as computers, internet connectivity, and adequate electricity supply. Lack of skills and motivation was also a challenge in implementing effective online learning. Recovering from the challenges requires a strategic planning process by the various stakeholders to develop measures that will aid in healing the lost time and prepare for similar education disruptions in the future.

Keywords: Afghanistan, COVID-19, Education System, Obstacles

Introduction

The outbreak of the novel Coronavirus pandemic, commonly known as Covid-19, in late 2019 had negatively impacted the social and economic progress of many countries globally. The pandemic became a full-blown global health emergency in early 2020, prompting several governments to take preventive actions to slow the rate of infections.¹The efforts to mitigate the spread of the virus by promoting social distancing protocols led to the closure of significant businesses, suspension of local and international flights, urban transportation, lockdowns, and suspension of the school

¹ World Health Organization. "WHO releases guidelines to help countries maintain essential health services during the COVID-19 pandemic." (March 2020). <<https://www.who.int/news/item/30-03-2020-who-releases-guidelines-to-help-countries-maintain-essential-health-services-during-the-covid-19-pandemic>>

calendars in many countries.² The closure of the learning institutions has mostly derailed the learning process, with the students having to stay at home for a prolonged period, while other institutions opting for virtual learning through modern technology platforms.³

The education calendar had equally been disrupted in Afghanistan due to the Covid-19 pandemic.⁴ Afghanistan's Ministry of Higher Education (MoHE) has strived to improve the education system and reduce the illiteracy level in the country since 2002.⁵ However, plans to increase the literacy rate in the country were significantly affected by the onset of the virus. Afghanistan's government recommended using the Higher Education Learning Management System (HELMS) online learning tool to facilitate distance learning while the schools remained closed due to the pandemic.⁶ Despite the measures, the closure of the learning institutions in Afghanistan had affected the education system in the country, primarily due to the lack of adequate infrastructure to aid online and distance teaching.⁷ The problem is worsened because the MoHE Afghanistan lacks sufficient infrastructure such as laptops and internet connectivity to facilitate online and distance teaching.⁸ Furthermore, students in remote areas of the country were disadvantaged due to the lack of electricity connectivity that could facilitate distance learning.⁹ The Covid-19 pandemic is affecting social and economic progress in the worst possible way, and recovering from the financial setback is a process that might take a long time.¹⁰

Similarly, the education sector continues to suffer as the efforts to facilitate school re-opening faces challenges as most

² Emre Aytakin, "Steps taken by countries in fighting COVID-19 pandemic." 2020.

<https://www.aa.com.tr/en/health/steps-taken-by-countries-in-fighting-covid-19-pandemic/1812009>

³ Sumiitra Pokhrel & Roshan Chhetri, "A Literature Review on Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Teaching and Learning." *Sage Perspectives*, 8 no. 1(2021):133-141.

⁴ Aisha Mohammadi, "Distance Learning in Afghanistan; Challenges and Policy Recommendations." *CSRS Policy Paper 2*, 2020. <https://csrskabul.com/en/wp-content/uploads/sites/2/2020/08/CSRS-English-Policy-Paper-Distance-Learning-in-Afghanistan.pdf>.

⁵ Rie Koarai, Samim, Yasin Mohammad, Shaahpor, Rafiullar. "Afghanistan: Continuing literacy and non-formal education for youth and adults during the COVID-19 crisis." *GPE*, August, 2020.

⁶ Mohammadi, "Distance Learning in Afghanistan; Challenges and Policy Recommendations." 2020

⁷ Koarai, 2020.

⁸ Mustapha Kamel Mohammadi, Abdul Aziz Mohibbi & Mohamed Hadi Hedayati, "Investigating the challenges and factors influencing the use of the learning management system during the Covid-19 pandemic in Afghanistan." *Education and Information Technology*, 2021.

⁹ Shugufa Khalil Basij-Rashikh and Safi Najibulla Merette, "Early responses to COVID-19 in Afghanistan." *EMHJ*, 26 no.12 (2020): 1442-1445.

<https://applications.emro.who.int/emhij/v26/12/1020-3397-2020-2612-1442-1445-eng.pdf?ua=1>

¹⁰ Abel Brodeur, Andrew Clark, Sarah Fleche, S., & Nattavuth Powdthavee, "COVID-19, Lockdowns and WellBeing: Evidence from Google Trends." In *Working Papers (No. 2004E; Working Papers)*. University of Ottawa, Department of Economics. 2020a.

institutions lack the facilities required to implement the recommended public health practices. While there is an extensive study on Covid-19 that mainly focusing on the epidemiological understanding of the pandemic and the related social and economic impacts that the pandemic has caused, limited research has been carried out to determine how the outbreak of the Covid-19 had affected the education sector, especially in countries such as Afghanistan, that are struggling with other social issues that stimulate the increase in illiteracy levels. The research gap identified for this study is the lack of extensive research on the impacts of the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic on the education system in Afghanistan, especially as the learning institutions strive to transition to distance learning. Based on these issues, the research seeks to analyse the impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic on the education system in Afghanistan. Furthermore, the usage of online learning platforms in addressing the challenges is explored as well.

1.1 Study Design

In this study, a qualitative research design was used as it helps in collecting real-life experiences that could be described numerically. As the research questions were exploratory, semi-structured interviews were utilized to collect information from a sample of 11 participants representing different entities in the education system. Thematic analysis was used to identify patterns and themes related to how the Covid-19 outbreak has affected the education system in Afghanistan.

2. Review of Literature

The outbreak of Covid-19 has affected people's lives across the world. The pandemic has impacted many facets of everyday life and prompted many countries to implement emergency response systems to curb the spread of the disease.¹¹ Education is an integral part of society and the foundation for social and economic growth. Yet, the temporary halt of the academic calendar as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic had led to massive disruption of education activities in most countries.¹² The first drastic measure that most countries implemented to prevent the pandemic spread included

¹¹ Wunong Zhang, Yuxin Wang, Lili Yang & Chuanyi Wang, "Suspending classes without stopping learning: China's education emergency management policy in the COVID-19 outbreak". *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, Vol. 13 No.3, (2020): 55.

¹² Mohammadi, "Investigating the challenges and factors influencing the use of the learning management system during the Covid-19 pandemic in Afghanistan." 3.

deciding to close all the public and private learning institutions. The criteria to contain the spread of Covid-19 put over one billion children at risk of falling behind the school calendar globally.¹³ The UNICEF report further indicates that; of the affected children, approximately 10 percent were unlikely to resume school due to factors such as the lack of finances, venturing into economic activities, and early marriages.¹⁴ In Afghanistan, the closure of schools due to the pandemic affected over 7.5 million children from public schools and over half a million children in community-based education (CBE).¹⁵

The most noticeable impact of Covid-19 is that the pandemic has exposed the inequalities experienced in our education system. The inadequacies between the privileged and disadvantaged students were highlighted as schools strived to shift to alternative measures to ensure continuity in the learning process.¹⁶ Some of the highlighted inadequacies include access to the facilities required to facilitate online learning, misalignment between resources and needs, and a supportive environment to support distance learning.¹⁷ The slowdown of the economic growth resulting from the pandemic had further affected some students as they had to look for income-earning ventures to support their families, thus increasing the chances of dropouts.¹⁸

Perhaps shifting the strategy was the most viable method that learning institutions could use to ensure continuity in learning as most schools had adopted the use of online and distance learning initiatives by using online tools such Google Classroom, WhatsApp, Zoom, and media channels to ensure that the students continue with the syllabus.¹⁹ Some higher learning institutions had adopted e-learning tools to help students continue learning when the schools were closed.²⁰ However, one of the significant challenges that face most learning institutions is the internal problem of adjusting to a remote learning environment and effectively

¹³ UNICEF. "Afghanistan Humanitarian Situation Report, No.3". January, 2020. <https://www.unicef.org/media/93136/file/Afghanistan-SitRep-YearEnd-2020.pdf>

¹⁴ UNICEF, 2020

¹⁵ UNICEF "Education and COVID-19". September 2020. <https://data.unicef.org/topic/education/covid-19/>

¹⁶ Schleicher, A.. "The Impact of Covid-19 on Education-Insights from Education at a Glance 2020. OECD." 2020 <https://www.oecd.org/education/the-impact-of-covid-19-on-education-insights-education-at-a-glance-2020.pdf>

¹⁷ Schleicher, 6

¹⁸ Mohammadi, "Distance Learning in Afghanistan; Challenges and Policy Recommendations." 5

¹⁹ Ahmad Kamal. Alif, Shaipulah, Mohd. "Transitioning to Online Learning during COVID-19 Pandemic: Case Study of a Pre-University Centre in Malaysia." *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 11, No. 6 (2020):217-223.

²⁰ Pokhrel and Chetri, 141.

utilizing online infrastructure to facilitate virtual learning.²¹ Online learning can only be effective if there is the availability of the necessary tools and knowledge. Unfortunately, most students, especially in low and middle-income countries such as Afghanistan, do not have access to essential devices such as computers, internet connectivity, and electricity to facilitate online learning.²²

Similarly, although e-learning has proved to be an effective tool in modern learning, the method faces significant challenges, including the inattentiveness and boredom of the learners as it reduces social interactions between people.²³ The effectiveness of e-learning can also be affected by the learners' and instructors' lack of knowledge and skills and the necessary resources such as computers, the internet, electricity, and learning software.

The implementation of online learning in Afghanistan has been affected by these factors, according to research.²⁴ Successful performance of online and remote learning process and the use of higher education learning management system (HELMS) was affected by significant challenges including lack of the necessary online learning tools as a result of poor economic conditions, high prices of internet, distrust about e-learning by the students and families, and lack of support by the government in providing the necessary infrastructure.²⁵ Further, academic performance is likely to be affected due to the reduced face-to-face contact between the learners and the teachers.²⁶ The issue is expected to affect vulnerable groups and children with other responsibilities such as taking care of their siblings and other household chores that limit their ability to attend CBE classes.

The world economy also was greatly affected by the declaration of Covid-19 as a global pandemic in early 2020. Economic development is primarily dependent on local and international trade relations and foreign direct investment.²⁷ The World Bank's report (2020) indicates that the policies put in place by the governments to reduce the spread of Covid-19 had resulted

²¹ Mohammadi, "Distance Learning in Afghanistan; Challenges and Policy Recommendations." 6.

²² Mohammadi, 24.

²³ Ala Alariqi, Abdulhakim, Khaneshpour, Homeira, Pashazadeh, Merhdad, Naziri, Rozita, "Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): review study." *Jorjani Biomedicine Journal*, 7no.4 (2020): 17-23. DOI: 10.29252/jorjanibiomedj.8.1.4.

²⁴ Mohammadi, 2020

²⁵ Mohammadi, 24

²⁶ Abolfazl Jafari Sales, Khaneshpour, Homeira, Pashazadeh, Merhdad, Naziri, Rozita, "Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19): review study." *Jorjani Biomedicine Journal*, 7no.4 (2020): 17-23. DOI: 10.29252/jorjanibiomedj.8.1.4.

²⁷ The World Bank. "The Impact of the Covid-19 Pandemic on Education Financing." May 2020. <https://pubdocs.worldbank.org/en/734541589314089887/Covid-and-Ed-Finance-final.pdf>

in tightening financial conditions, trade disruptions, direct costs associated with hospitalization, and a massive demand and supply shock. Consequently, the closure of businesses has led to massive retrenchment and unemployment.²⁸ The increased cases of unemployment and underemployment had further threatened the survival tactics of many people across the globe. Other factors that stimulate economic growth, including quality education, were also affected adversely.²⁹ The rate of deaths resulting from an epidemic outbreak, such as caused by the 1918 influenza outbreak, could significantly reduce GDP and a decline in private consumption.³⁰

The effort to contain the spread of Covid-19 has also affected fiscal policy and public sector financing. Most countries have been implementing financing policies to address immediate social and health.³¹ These include financing research programs and public vaccination plans, public health awareness initiatives, and providing the public with PPEs and hand-washing facilities, especially in populated settlement areas.³² As a result, the reduction in the education budget further limits the ability of the public schools and higher learning institutions to fund the hygiene and physical distancing initiatives that could aid in the partial and or full reopening of schools.³³

3. Methodology

This study utilized a qualitative research approach that involved asking open-ended questions that correspond with the research questions and an in-depth understanding of the various clarifications and understanding of different observations. A qualitative approach was chosen as the most suitable method for this study as it could help to gain a deeper understanding of the personal experiences and reflections based on individual's feelings of how Covid-19 had disrupted the learning process and also to gain insights on different views on how the situation could be addressed collectively. The research utilized interviews as the most appropriate research instrument to gain more in-depth insights

²⁸ Schleicher, 9

²⁹ Koarai, "Afghanistan: Continuing literacy and non-formal education for youth and adults during the COVID-19 crisis." 1.

³⁰ Robert Barro J, Jose Ursua F and Joanna Weng. "The Coronavirus and the Great Influenza Epidemic - Lessons from the "Spanish Flu" for the Coronavirus's Potential Effects on Mortality and Economic Activity." *CESifo Working Paper Series 8166*, 2020. https://ideas.repec.org/p/ces/ceswps/_8166.html

³¹ The World Bank, 2020

³² Francesco Di Gennaro and Damiano Pizzol, "Coronavirus Diseases (COVID-19) Current Status and Future Perspectives: A Narrative Review." *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17, No. 8 (2020): 2690. doi:10.3390/ijerph17082690

³³ The World Bank, 2020

from the individuals. Semi-structured interviews were selected for the study, and the participants were interviewed through Skype due to the travel and physical distance restrictions associated with Covid-19. Semi-structured interviews give the interviewer freedom to probe and develop rapport with the interviewee while giving them the freedom to explore additional questions that can help in gaining more insight and get significant replies.³⁴

The sampling approach used in the study aimed at collecting data from individuals representing various sectors that are directly and indirectly involved in the education system and curriculum development. A purposive sampling method was used to select a good correspondence that could provide a broader range of answers to the research questions. 11 participants were interviewed through Skype, comprising eight university professors and associate professors, one education officer, a UNICEF education officer specialist. The data collection process lasted for one month, where the interviews commenced on first and ended on April 30, 2021. All the interviews with a participant lasted for approximately one hour. The conversation between the researcher and the interviewees was stored in a voice recording to allow easy decoding and analysis of the data.

4. Results

A thematic analysis of the results is presented below, and textual fragments obtained from the study participants were used to reinforce the results. Research participants gave almost similar views on the significant concerns regarding Covid-19 and how the pandemic has affected the education system in Afghanistan. The first theme presented from the study is the impacts of Covid-19 on the education system.

4.1 Impacts of Covid-19 on Education System

4.1.1 Considerable Learning Loss

All the participants felt that Covid-19 had negatively affected and delayed the normal education timeline. The most highlighted impacts of the pandemic include the halt in education calendars, lack of effective distance learning techniques due to the lack of family and social support, and economic strains. Learners were also affected by the disruption as they had to halt the academic calendar temporarily. Learners were reported to miss regular study

³⁴Alan Bryman, *Social Research Methods. (2nd Ed.)*. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2004).

timetable while other students were subject to poor health as one participant points out:

In the short term, it messed the regular study timetable of the university and schools. Lack of access the schools and universities had negatively affected the health and wellbeing of the students. (Officer of Ministry of Education Kabul provinces).

4.1.2 The Ineffective Remote Learning Process

Although some universities had implemented online and remote learning to ensure that learners were not left behind, the e-learning plan was not as efficient as previously predicted. The majority of the participants stated that the lack of infrastructure and electricity in the country had contributed to the ineffectiveness in implementing online and distance learning to cover the lost learning time after the closure of the schools.

Unfortunately, due to the lack of facilities, distance education or virtual education is not available. Many students do not have electricity. Lack of electricity and the internet accessibility are the impediments further worsening the online educational setup. (Assistant Professor Communication & Journalism School, Kabul University)

Some of the challenges noted to contribute to the flawed remote learning process included lack of access to IT and connectivity, lack of students' motivation to engage in online learning, lack of provision of virtual content, and lack of societal support.

4.1.3 Ineffective Online Learning

All the study participants pointed out that; although online learning was implemented successfully in other developed countries, the method has not been effective in Afghanistan. The reasons for the ineffectiveness include lack of resources and infrastructure to facilitate online learning, lack of skills by the instructors, and lack of motivation.

Virtual learning was not effective because access to the internet is challenging; we have no access to the internet in many areas. However, in some regions, there is an internet connectivity, but it is feeble. Besides, internet cost is the other factor affecting virtual learning efficiency. In addition to this, even teachers are also not familiar with the internet and the English language. (Associate Professor of Khost University).

Furthermore, some education officials felt that the education institutions in Afghanistan were not fully prepared to roll out

online teaching. In contrast, other factors such as poor internet connection and lack of online tools among the students frustrated the use of the HELMS system for online learning:

The Ministry of Higher Education of our country has designed the HELMS system for online education. Still, due to the low quality of the internet, it often cannot be used effectively. (Associate Professor Agronomy Department, Takhar University)

4.1.4 Inadequate Preparedness to re-open Schools and Deliver Quality Education

The study participants also pointed out that most schools were not prepared to re-open schools, especially amid the pandemic. While regular studies have resumed in some institutions, issues such as the lack of adequate facilities to facilitate hygiene protocols and enhance social distancing by the students could make it hard to prevent the spread of the virus. When asked if schools were prepared to re-open and if they will be able to observe social distancing, one of the interviewees replied that;

Based on my experience and coinciding with published UNICEF, save the children, UNDP, and SIGAR reports, shows the schools in Afghanistan not stuffiest hygiene and health toolkit during in Emergences.... During my visit from schools in the field, children were not observing the social distance, even in a populated area. (UNICEF Afghanistan Education Officer at Kabul province)

All the participants also recommended government intervention to provide the necessary facilities to facilitate online re-opening and enable distance learning in instances that require schools to remain closed or partially open.

The government should assist and help the institutions. The education institutions do not have the means to do it by themselves. (Associate professor at Agriculture faculty of Ghazni University).

However, some education officials felt that the government might not help rebuild the education system in Afghanistan due to factors such as insecurity and lack of adequate resources.

The government does not have enough resources to step in and help the education system. (Expert in Education for Kabul province)

4.1.5 Strategies to Cover for the Lost Time

Some of the strategies suggested by the interviewees include increasing education programs through TVs and radios, expanding

the learning duration after re-opening schools, coordinating with parents, and focusing more on significant subjects.

The possible strategies are intensive education or learning, focus on the student's demands, parents' focus on the school and teachers' demand, cooperation, and coordination of the parents with schools and educational centres. (Associate Professor, Animal Science Department- Faculty of Agriculture, Nangarhar University).

Further, some faculty noted that; to cover for the lost time, both the students and educators need to sacrifice more time for the studies for more hours and increase homework for the students. One participant also noted that the teachers should simplify the lessons to make the content easy to understand. An officer from the Ministry of Education (Kabul Provinces) stated that teachers should

"Increase students' homework, provide the lessons more simply and shortly, made the students study and do the most of the lessons and force them to participate in education projects."

Discussion and Conclusion

The main objectives of this qualitative study were to highlight the impacts of Covid-19 on the education system in Afghanistan and how online learning has helped address the challenges caused by the pandemic. Based on the study results, all the participants felt that the education system was negatively affected after the drastic measures to close all the learning institutions were implemented³⁵. The results of the schools' closure include haltered academic calendar, psychological problems among the students due to the fear of having to resume school, and the economic burden for the private institutions that had to pay bills despite the disruption in their source of income. The schools' closure results include a haltered academic calendar, psychological problems among the students due to the fear of having to resume school, and the economic burden for the private institutions that had to pay bills despite the disruption in their source of income. Further, the data collected portrays that online and distance learning is an effective learning tool that could aid in curriculum continuity while the students were at home. It had not proved to be effective in Afghanistan. The results pointed out that most students lack the necessary resources such as personal computers, internet connection, and electricity supply to foster online learning.³⁶

³⁵ Mohammadi "Distance Learning in Afghanistan; Challenges and Policy Recommendations." 6.

³⁶ Kamal, 223

Furthermore, the worsening economic conditions worsen the situation as most families cannot afford to pay for electricity and internet bills to facilitate online learning. In contrast, such harsh economic conditions had prompted some students to look for income-earning activities³⁷.

The lack of skills by the educators in utilizing online learning tools made it challenging to implement virtual learning. In contrast, the social setting where most students are located in remote areas made it challenging to utilize media platforms such as radios and TVs to implement distance learning.³⁸

Concerning the preparedness by the institutions to re-open the schools amidst the Covid-19 pandemic, the study shows that most institutions were not prepared, especially since most institutions in the country lack the essential facilities to implement hygiene measures. The study shows that most people lack public awareness or ignore the basic social distancing and hygiene standards, and this could be a risk factor that could affect schools' re-opening. Results further indicate that long-term initiatives to foster online learning could aid in ensuring learning continuity in case of the closure of the learning institutions. Some measures could show the need for government intervention in facilitating learning institutions and equipping them with the necessary resources to cope with curriculum disruptions.³⁹

Allocating more funding and partnering with the local governments and NGOs such as UNICEF could facilitate learning, especially in remote areas.⁴⁰

However, some participants noted that the government might not finance the education system due to factors such as the insecurity issues affecting the country and lack of adequate resources to finance other pressing sectors such as health and social support services. Consequently, such problems could indicate that the social factors that affect the effectiveness of the education system, including the inadequate learning resources and insecurity, could hinder the effective learning process and the ravaging effects of Covid-19.⁴¹

To conclude, the emergence of the novel Coronavirus has negatively affected the education system in Afghanistan, as the

³⁷ Kamal 223

³⁸ Mohammadi, "Investigating the challenges and factors influencing the use of the learning management system during the Covid-19 pandemic in Afghanistan." 27

³⁹ Alariqi, 2019

⁴⁰ Schleicher, 8

⁴¹ Shivangi, Dhawan. "Online learning: A panacea in the time of COVID-19 crises." *Journal of Educational Technology*, 49, no.1 (2020): 5–22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047239520934018>

strict control measures that led to the closure of public and private learning institutions altered the school program in the country. Previous literature indicates that the deteriorating economic situation and Covid-19 containment measures had affected education plans.⁴²

The study results also suggest that the lack of preparedness by the schools to provide the necessary online learning tools, lack of basic hygiene facilities, and adequate space to implement social distancing is a social problem that could hinder the effective re-opening of schools. Such issues indicate that the Ministry of Education and other education stakeholders should develop strategic policy implementation plans that could aid in preparing for possible challenges that could disrupt the education system in the future. The first step to ensure effective transitioning to online learning is creating an organizational culture that promotes both traditional and modern digital learning⁴³.

Such culture includes equal access to affordable online learning tools and resources such as electricity and internet connectivity, promoting a culture that fosters knowledge acquisition, and providing alternative software and online forums that are easy to access. Further, boosting online and distance learning culture will reduce barriers such as boredom and lack of acceptance of online learning techniques by the students and families.⁴⁴

Study Limitations

While using a qualitative research approach was effective in collecting personalized findings, several limitations were highlighted. Although the sample allowed for representations from different sectors directly involved in the education system in Afghanistan, it failed to capture the opinions of the students who were directly affected by the closure of the schools due to Covid-19.

The sample size also increased the risk of researcher bias. Researcher bias occurs when the researcher skews the study results towards a specific research outcome. However, the data collection method allowed more room for interpretation, thus reducing the risks of researcher bias. While the study has provided

⁴² Sales, 19.

⁴³ Taat, Mohamad, Suhaimi, & Francis, Agatha. "Factors influencing the students' acceptance of E-Learning at teacher education institute: An exploratory study in Malaysia." *International Journal of Higher Education*, 9, no.1 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.5430/ijhe.v9n1p133>.

⁴⁴ Taat and Francis 3.

a clearer understanding of the current implication of Covid-19 on the education system in Afghanistan and the ongoing strategies to overcome the impacts, further studies should be conducted to investigate how training and awareness on information technology could aid in promoting distance learning.

About the Author

Mr. Mohammad Ajmal Khuram, Graduate School of Humanities and Social Sciences 1-1-1 Kagamiyama, Higashi-Hiroshima City, Hiroshima, 739-8524, Japan.